

NON-RENEWABLE AND RENEWABLE EXERGY FOOTPRINTS OF DIESEL AND ELECTRIC-POWERED FREIGHT TRANSPORTATION SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

As the mobility sector transitions toward sustainability, evaluating the exergy costs of various transportation systems has become increasingly important. For that reason, this study assesses exergy consumption in freight transportation, comparing diesel and electric-powered trains with road freight transportation, using both diesel and electricity as energy sources. The research evaluates the exergy required to produce the materials used in both diesel and electric trains, including steel, aluminum, and lithium for electric batteries. It also considers the infrastructure needed for each technology. In addition, road freight transportation, using both diesel and electricity, is analyzed to compare its material composition, energy demands, and operational efficiency throughout its lifespan. By integrating both direct fuel consumption and the exergy costs of materials, this study provides a comprehensive analysis of the energy requirements for different transportation modes. The results show that diesel-electric trains are not highly dependent on infrastructure, but they exhibit high operational exergy costs due to the lower efficiency of fossil fuel combustion. Road freight, while requiring simpler infrastructure, remains heavily reliant on fossil fuels, resulting in higher long-term operational exergy consumption. This analysis highlights the importance of considering both operational and material-related exergy costs when evaluating transportation systems. The findings offer valuable insights for optimizing resource use and advancing the energy transition in the mobility sector.

Keywords: Exergy costs; Freight transportation; Infrastructure; Materials; Thermoeconomics.

1 INTRODUCTION

The global transition to clean energy and the growing electrification of transportation have intensified the demand for critical metals such as lithium, cobalt, nickel, and rare earth elements (Woodley et al., 2023). These materials are fundamental to the production of electric vehicle (EV) batteries and the expansion of renewable energy infrastructure (Coppens, 2023). Projections from the International Energy Agency (IEA, 2022) indicate that the need for these metals could rise by a factor of five by 2040, presenting substantial challenges related to resource availability and the environmental impact of their extraction and processing. Although these developments play a key role in mitigating climate change, they also necessitate a rigorous analysis of their long-term sustainability and material efficiency (Natural Resources Division, 2024).

Additionally, beyond the direct consequences of resource extraction, the shift toward electric transportation affects energy and material consumption across the entire lifespan of transportation systems (Torrubia et al., 2024b). Efficient planning and management of freight transportation can significantly reduce tonne-kilometres (t · kms), thereby lowering environmental impact and operational costs. Strategies such as local sourcing and decentralized storage help minimize the need for long-distance transportation (Srinivas Ganesh & Patil, 2025). Additionally, increasing vehicle utilization by

avoiding empty or partially loaded truck trips presents a key opportunity to improve the efficiency of logistics systems.

Material consumption in European freight transport by truck is projected to increase from 2020 to 2050, as the truck fleet's share of battery electric vehicles (BE) is expected to rise from 0.2% to 26.1% (Klimt, 2024). This shift will result in a higher environmental impact due to the significantly greater consumption of metallic materials, particularly copper and gold, in BE trucks compared to internal combustion engine (ICE-diesel) trucks, owing to the battery and battery management system.

The electrification of trains is a viable solution, as the electrical grid, sourced from various energy resources, can transmit power to the wheels with a high degree of energy efficiency. Moreover, more than half of the railway lines are electrified in several European countries, including Spain. For instance, in Switzerland, the electrification rate is close to 100% due to the country's vast hydropower resources (Lucas & Busso, 2007).

In contrast, the environmental impacts of freight rail transport tend to decrease, as the high efficiency of catenary electric (CE) locomotives results in only minor increases in electricity consumption per tonne-kilometre (t·km) by 2050 (European Commission, 2019; UNFCCC, 2015). In Europe, electrification rates of the locomotive fleet increase from 39.6% to 57.0% within the period from 2020 to 2025 (Klimt, 2024). This is primarily due to the transition from internal combustion engine diesel-electric (ICE-de) locomotives to catenary electric (CE) locomotives. This transition does not require increased material consumption, as CE locomotives do not rely on onboard energy storage, as is the case for battery electric trucks, but instead use a catenary system for direct energy supply. Furthermore, operating one or more locomotives alongside several freight wagons makes rail transport more material-efficient per tonne-kilometre than its road-based counterpart.

In previous studies, (Fumasoli et al., 2015) analyzed the operational and technical challenges of operating freight trains in densely used railway networks, against the background of capacity consumption. The purpose of this study is to outline the effects of improved rolling stock on capacity consumption in mixed-traffic railway networks. Many approaches to railway capacity can be found in the literature. (Burdett & Kozan, 2006) for instance propose a method to determine absolute capacity. From a comparative Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) perspective, rail freight transport has been shown to have lower environmental impacts than road freight transport (Nahlik et al., 2016; Negri et al., 2022), while integrating new technologies to decarbonize the sector (Jaramillo Paulina et al., 2023). Moreover, environmental impacts are likely to shift towards upstream supply chains and impact categories unrelated to climate change (Kurada et al., 2023), reinforcing the need for a prospective Life Cycle Assessment (pLCA) to compare transport modes.

Road transport (both passenger and freight) has been analyzed in previous LCA studies using prospective scenarios (Dirnaichner et al., 2022; Sacchi et al., 2021). However, in the case of freight transport, comparisons focused on specific technologies without considering vehicle fleet compositions. (Logan et al., 2021) conducted one of the first prospective comparative assessments of electric and hybrid trains up to 2050, but it only addressed energy consumption and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

In this context, (Klimt, 2024) analyzed the prospective environmental impacts of global rail freight transport throughout its life cycle, comparing it to road freight transport in 2050. This is directly related to the present study, which aims to compare the material and energy consumption of road and rail freight transport from a thermodynamic perspective (Valero et al., 2021). Consequently, this study assesses the material and exergy implications of transport electrification, focusing on resource efficiency and sustainability throughout the lifecycle of freight transport and its infrastructure. The exergy costs of materials are analyzed per kilometre travelled and per ton transported in road and rail systems, comparing diesel and electricity as energy carriers.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

In this section, a physical method for allocating exergy costs in metal production is applied, based on the work of Torrubia and collaborators (Torrubia et al., 2023). The approach relies on the relative geological scarcity of elements in the Earth's crust, which forms the basis for assigning exergy costs, a key aspect for understanding the scope of this study. The exergy cost represents the amount of exergy (useful energy) consumed to produce a material or product. In the context of this study, the exergy cost is calculated by considering the main stages of metal production, which include: Mining and Concentration (M&C), Smelting and Refining (S&R) and the Energy Footprint of Chemicals (EFC). The method estimates the energy and carbon footprint of 51 metals, including 28 co-products, using data from established databases (Nassar et al., 2015). Moreover, the analysis accounts for fuel type (natural gas, diesel, coal, and electricity and the energy intensity of up to 25 associated chemicals. This methodology provides a robust framework for evaluating the efficiency and sustainability of energy conversion processes and serves as a key parameter in the allocation of exergy costs.

Subsequently, the methodology used in this study to assess the exergy cost per tonne-kilometre transported for the transport modes under analysis is presented. To ensure transparency and reproducibility, this step-by-step process outlines the procedures followed to calculate and compare exergy consumption across the different transportation systems considered in this study.

2.1 Methodology Description

After defining the approach used to allocate the exergy cost of metals among different energy sources, the methodology developed for this purpose is presented. The structure of this method is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Diagram of the steps followed in the methodology used in the study

First, the case studies were defined based on data availability. The primary objective was to evaluate freight trucks and freight trains powered by two types of fuels: diesel and electricity. However, for fully electric trains, material composition data was not available. Since the aim of this study is to calculate the exergy costs of materials per kilometre travelled and per tonne transported in road and rail transport systems, comparing diesel and electricity as energy carriers, the selected case studies are: Freight truck with an internal combustion engine (ICE), Battery-electric freight truck (BE) and Freight train with a combination of an internal combustion engine and battery-electric propulsion (ICE-BE).

- Freight truck (ICE): Data for this case was obtained from two different sources: Freight truck (ICE) (1), from the ecoinvent database, specifically the dataset “Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO3 | transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO3 | APOS, U - RER”, (ecoinvent, 2023), accessible via the OpenLCA v2.2.0 software. And Freight truck (ICE) (2), from the study by (Lommahadthai, 2023), an alternative source to ecoinvent was sought to enable a comparative analysis of the material compositions of diesel freight trucks, ensuring more rigorous and comprehensive information.
- Battery-electric freight truck (BE): Data for this category was sourced from the same study as the previous case (Lommahadthai, 2023) due to the high level of detail provided. Additionally, no relevant information for battery-electric freight trucks was available in the ecoinvent database.
- Freight train (ICE-BE): To estimate the total metallic mass of this transport mode, data was retrieved from the ecoinvent database, specifically from the dataset “Freight train, diesel transport, freight train | APOS, U - Europe without Switzerland”, (ecoinvent, 2023), accessible via OpenLCA v2.2.0, along with several assumptions based on ecoinvent’s available data.

Once the case studies have been defined, the next step involves allocating these costs among the various energy sources and metal production stages. In this study, the production stages have been grouped according to the four energy sources considered: natural gas (NG), diesel, coal, and electricity.

Based on the mass of metals comprising the freight transport modes analyzed in this study, and using the disaggregated energy footprint by fuel type (MJ/kg) provided by (Torrubia et al., 2024a), the exergy cost associated with the consumption of natural gas, diesel, coal and electricity is calculated for each metal. To perform these calculations, energy to exergy conversion factors, as listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Exergy conversion factors (ExCF) $\text{MJ}_{\text{exergy}}/\text{MJ}_{\text{energy}}$ of each source (Font de Mora et al., 2012; Hall et al., 2014; Valero & Valero, 2012)

Year	NG	Diesel	Coal	Electricity
2020	1.06	1.07	1.04	1

As an example, for the case of the Fe content in the freight truck with an internal combustion engine (ICE), the exergy cost associated with natural gas (excluding both the maximum load and the total distance travelled) is calculated according to Equation (1).

$$Ex_{mat} = e_{mat}(ES) \cdot M_{mat} \cdot \text{ExCF} \quad (1)$$

$$Ex_{Fe} = 1.18 \cdot 1.30\text{E}+04 \cdot 1.06 = \mathbf{1.63\text{E}+04 \text{ MJ}}$$

It is important to note that the sum of the exergy contributions from the different energy sources corresponds to the energy footprint of each metal, expressed in MJ according to Equation (2). For the aforementioned case, the result is:

$$EF_{mat} = Ex_{mat}(NG) + Ex_{mat}(Diesel) + Ex_{mat}(Coal) + Ex_{mat}(Electricity) \quad (2)$$

$$EF_{Fe} = 1.63\text{E}+04 + 5.68\text{E}+03 + 2.41\text{E}+05 + 5.44\text{E}+04 = \mathbf{3.17\text{E}+05 \text{ MJ}}$$

The ecoinvent database provides information on a diesel-electric freight train featuring locomotives of the "Re 460" type, which are currently used for both passenger and freight transportation in Switzerland (SBB - Lokomotiven, 2018). Based on its technical characteristics and the European Commission Implementing Regulation of August 10, 2023 (European Commission, 2023), a standard European freight train has been defined as consisting of two Re 460 locomotives and 25 wagons, with a maximum cargo capacity of 60 tonnes (SeaRates, 2025).

The necessary data to calculate the exergy costs of materials per kilometre travelled and per tonne transported in road and rail transport systems (ExC_{mat}) is calculated using Equation (3) and Table 2, comparing diesel and electricity as energy carriers, are as follows:

$$ExC_{mat} = \frac{Ex_{mat}}{MLC \cdot T_d} \quad (3)$$

Table 2: Key operational parameters for different freight transport modes

Parameter	Units	Freight ICE Trucks ¹	Freight BE Truck ²	Freight Train (ICE-BE) ³
Lifespan (L_f)	years	10	10	35
Annual distance (A_d)	km/year	96,872	75,000	100,000
Total distance (T_d)	km	968,720	750,000	3,500,000
Max. load capacity (MLC)	t (tonnes)	5.79	5.79	1,000

¹ (Lommahadthai, 2023).

² (Canals Casals et al., 2022).

³ (ecoinvent, 2023; European Commission, 2023; SBB - Lokomotiven, 2018; SeaRates, 2025).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Elemental composition and exergy costs of freight modes materials

Using the data provided by the various databases, the amount and percentage of different elements contained in each of the analyzed freight transport modes were determined. Figure 2 shows the exergy costs of materials per tonne-kilometre in road and rail systems, comparing diesel and electricity as energy carriers. The upper section shows the Non-Renewable energy sources (NG, diesel and coal) while the lower section displays the Renewable energy fraction (Renewable Electricity) for the elements composing the freight vehicle's parts.

Figure 2: Exergy cost (MJ/t-km) evaluated and classified as non-renewable and renewable for the elements composing the analyzed freight transport modes. a), e) Freight truck (1) (ICE); b), f) Freight truck (2); c), g) Battery-electric freight truck (BE); d), h) Freight train (ICE-BE)

In the case of non-renewable sources (a–d), Fe clearly dominates the exergy cost contribution across all transport systems. Freight train (ICE-BE) shows the highest proportion of Fe, accounting for 87% of the total exergy cost, followed by Freight truck (1) with 84%. Freight Truck (2) and the Battery-Electric Truck exhibit lower Fe shares, with 68% and 52%, respectively. The presence of other elements such as Mn, Cr, and Ni is more limited, generally below 11%, although Ni in the Battery-Electric Truck reaches a relevant 11%.

When considering renewable electricity as the energy source (e–h), a shift in exergy cost distribution is observed. In Freight Truck (2), Al becomes even more dominant, rising to 71% of the total exergy cost, while in the Battery-Electric Truck (g) it reaches 55%. Cr also gains importance under renewable energy scenarios, reaching 5% in Freight Truck (2) and 6% in the BE Freight Truck. In contrast, the Freight Train still shows a significant Fe contribution, accounting for 50%. However, other elements such as Al, Cr, Cu, and Si also gain relevance.

These results highlight the significant role of Fe in the overall exergy footprint of freight transport modes, particularly under non-renewable energy sources. However, when renewable electricity is used, the contribution of other metals becomes more pronounced, especially in electrified systems, due to the material complexity and the need for critical metals such as Mn, Cr, and Ni.

Figure 3, shows the total exergy cost per ton for the materials used in different freight transport modes, classified by energy source: non-renewable (grey) and renewable (green). Additionally, the black dots represent the total material cost of metals used in each transport mode (right axis).

Figure 3: Analysis of exergy cost (MJ/t·km) for heavy-duty road and rail transport: ICE vs. BE

The Battery-Electric Freight Truck (BE) displays the highest total exergy cost, with a substantial contribution from renewable energy sources. This reflects the increased presence of metals like Ni and Co associated with battery components, which generally involve high exergy extraction costs due to their relative scarcity and energy-intensive processing. Freight Truck 1 (ICE) and Freight Truck 2 (ICE) show a similar distribution pattern, with exergy costs slightly lower than the BE truck. In both cases, non-renewable sources dominate, though renewable contributions are also notable. The difference between both ICE trucks lies mainly in the proportion of renewable energy usage and possibly variations in material composition. The Freight Train (ICE-BE) shows the lowest overall exergy cost among the four systems analyzed. Its relatively low material cost combined with a moderate renewable share suggests a more efficient material configuration. This is because both the payload and the total kilometres travelled throughout its useful life are higher than in the other cases. Despite being a hybrid system, its total exergy demand is more balanced.

Figure 4 compares the exergy cost associated with materials and fuel or energy consumption for four different freight transportation options: two internal combustion engine (ICE) trucks, one battery electric (BE) truck, and one hybrid ICE-BE freight train. The energy consumptions for the different cases are as follows: Freight Truck ICE (1) = 0.038 kg/t·km (Lommahadthai, 2023); Freight Truck ICE (2) = 0.4 L/km (Lommahadthai, 2023); Freight Truck (BE) = 1.28 kWh/km (Canals Casals et al., 2022); Freight Train (ICE-BE) = 0.011 kg/t·km (ecoinvent, 2023; European Commission, 2023; SBB - Lokomotiven, 2018; SeaRates, 2025). The following values were used for unit conversions: the higher heating value (HHV) of diesel is 44.8 MJ/kg and 38.6 MJ/L, and 1 kWh is equivalent to 3.6 MJ.

Figure 4: Comparison of material and energy consumption exergy costs (MJ/t·km) for heavy-duty road and rail transport: ICE vs. BE

The bar chart shows the exergy cost of materials is much lower than that related to energy consumption in all cases, and that the mode of transport with the highest total exergy cost is Freight Truck 2 (ICE) due to a substantial contribution from energy sources and a relatively minor one from materials. Freight Truck 1 (ICE) is slightly more efficient, although it still shows a high exergy cost, especially in terms of energy use. In contrast, the Battery Electric Freight Truck represents a substantial improvement, with noticeably lower exergy costs for both materials and energy sources. Most notably, the Freight Train (ICE-BE) emerges as the most efficient alternative, exhibiting the lowest total exergy cost thanks to its minimal reliance on both material and energy resources.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of exergy cost distribution for metals used in freight transport modes reveals several important trends. First, Fe, consistently constitutes the majority of the exergy burden among all transport systems, especially under non-renewable energy sources. Its dominance underscores its structural relevance but also highlights the potential for significant exergy savings through material efficiency or substitution.

The contribution of other metals such as Al and Ni become more significant in electrified transport systems, particularly when powered by renewable electricity. The battery-electric truck and the hybrid electric train show noticeable shares of Cr and Al, indicating their critical role in the energy transition. This shift suggests that as systems move away from fossil fuels, the material complexity and dependency on high-exergy-cost metals increase. Moreover, renewable electricity shifts the distribution of exergy costs slightly from being dominated by Fe to a more balanced mix of metals. This is especially evident in the electric Freight Truck, where Fe accounts for only 12% of the total, and other metals like Cr and Ni become more relevant.

In summary, the materials exergy cost results show that while electrification reduces operational exergy consumption, it may increase the material related exergy burden due to the need for more energy-

intensive and scarce metals. These findings highlight the importance of considering both operational and embodied exergy when assessing sustainable transport systems.

The results indicate that electrification, particularly in battery-electric vehicles, leads to higher material-related exergy costs. This increase is primarily driven by the use of specialized materials required for batteries, which are often obtained through energy-intensive processes. However, a notable share of this exergy demand can be supplied by renewable energy, partially mitigating environmental impact. Freight trains show lower overall exergy costs and material use, supporting their potential as a more resource-efficient freight transport alternative. This analysis underscores the importance of not only evaluating operational emissions, but also considering the embedded exergy in materials when comparing transport modes.

The comparative evaluation of transportation modes reveals that transitioning from traditional internal combustion engine freight trucks to battery electric or hybrid train systems can significantly reduce exergy costs. Energy source exergy costs dominate in all scenarios, but the use of more efficient or renewable energy in BE and hybrid systems shows a tangible advantage. Among the four options, the hybrid freight train stands out as the most sustainable choice in terms of resource efficiency.

5 FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Future research will explore electric freight trains and hydrogen fuel cell vehicles, which were excluded due to limited data on their material composition. The scope will also expand to other modes, such as ships and aircraft, for a more comprehensive assessment of environmental and material impacts across the sector.

NOMENCLATURE

The nomenclature should be located at the end of the text using the following format:

Abbreviation	Definition
A_d	Annual distance (km)
BE	Battery Electric
e_{mat}	Specific energy of materials (MJ/kg)
EFC	Energy Footprint of Chemicals (MJ)
EF_{mat}	Energy Footprint of materials (MJ)
ES	Energy Source
EV	Electric Vehicle
ExC_{mat}	Exergy cost of materials (MJ/t·km)
ExCF	Exergy Conversion Factor
Ex_{mat}	Exergy of materials (MJ)
HHV	High Heating Value (MJ/kg or MJ/L)
ICE	Internal Combustion Engine
ICE-BE	Internal Combustion Engine - Battery Electric
kJ	Kilojoules
L	Litres
Lf	Lifespan
MJ	Megajoules
MLC	Maximum Load Capacity
M&C	Mining and Concentration
NG	Natural Gas
S&R	Smelting and Refining
t	Tonnes
T_d	Total distance

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